

Research paper

Positive solutions for singular problems with multivalued convection

Yunru Bai ^{a,1}, Leszek Gasiński ^{b,1,*}, Nikolaos S. Papageorgiou ^{c,1}^a School of Science, Guangxi University of Science and Technology, Liuzhou 545006, Guangxi, China^b Department of Mathematics, University of the National Education Commission, Crakow, Podchorazych 2, 30-084 Kraków, Poland^c Department of Mathematics, National Technical University, Zografou Campus, Athens 15780, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

MSC:
35J92
35J30

Keywords:

Multivalued perturbation
Gradient dependence
Pseudomonotone operator
Truncation
Positive smooth solution

ABSTRACT

We consider an elliptic Dirichlet problem, driven by a general nonlinear, nonhomogeneous differential operator and a reaction that has the competing effects of a parametric singular term and of a multivalued perturbation which is gradient dependent (convection). Using truncations, comparisons and the theory of nonlinear operators of monotone type, we show that for all small values of the parameter $\lambda > 0$, the problem has a positive and smooth solution.

1. Introduction

Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^N$ be a bounded domain with a C^2 -boundary $\partial\Omega$. In this paper, we study the following singular Dirichlet inclusion

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div} a(Du(z)) \in \lambda u(z)^{-\eta} + F(z, u(z), Du(z)) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

with $\lambda > 0$ and $0 < \eta < 1$. In this equation, the map $a: \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ involved in the differential operator, is a continuous, strictly monotone (thus, maximal monotone) map, which satisfies certain other regularity and growth conditions dictated by the global (that is, up to the boundary) regularity theory of Lieberman [1]. These hypotheses on the map a , provide a general framework in which we can fit many differential operators of interest, such as the p -Laplacian and the (p, q) -Laplacian. Such differential operators were used by Papageorgiou–Rădulescu [2] for nonlinear nonhomogeneous Neumann problems, and by Papageorgiou–Rădulescu–Repovš [3] for nonlinear singular problems. The reaction of (1.1) exhibits the combined effects of a parametric singular term and of a multivalued convective perturbation. The fact that the multivalued perturbation depends on the gradient Du of the unknown function u , means that problem (1.1) is nonvariational and so our method of proof will be topological. More precisely, we will combine the method of upper–lower solutions with the theory of nonlinear operators of monotone type. While nonlinear elliptic equations with convection have been studied extensively, the study of nonlinear singular convective problems is lagging behind. We mention the works of Bai–Gasiński–Papageorgiou [4], Papageorgiou–Rădulescu–Repovš [5], Papageorgiou–Scapellato [6] and Papageorgiou–Zhang [7]. In all the aforementioned works, the perturbation is single-valued and in all, but [7], the driving differential operator, is the p -Laplacian.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: yunrubai@163.com (Y. Bai), leszek.gasinski@up.krakow.pl (L. Gasiński), npapg@math.ntua.gr (N.S. Papageorgiou).¹ The authors contributed equally to this paper.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cnsns.2023.107621>

Available online 13 October 2023

1007-5704/© 2023 The Author(s).

Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license

(<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

In addition the approach in these works is different and uses the fixed point theory, in particular the Leray–Schauder alternative principle and the method of the frozen variable. We mention the paper of Zeng–Liu–Migórski [8], which does not have a singular term, but the approach is similar to our method of proof.

Finally we mention the works of El Manouni–Marino–Winkert [9], Zeng–Papageorgiou [10], Zhang–Niu–Han [11]. In [9] the authors study convective double phase problems with nonlinear boundary condition of Robin–Steklov type. Using nonresonance conditions involving the principal Robin and Steklov eigenvalues, they prove existence and multiplicity results. In [10] the authors deal with a convective (p, q) -equation (balanced growth problem) and using fixed point theory, they produce a positive regular solutions. In [11] the problem is a system of Schrödinger–Poisson type in \mathbb{R}^3 and they prove a multiplicity theorem. We point out that none of the aforementioned works deals with singular problems. The recent survey paper of Papageorgiou [12] provides an overview of the necessary background to deal with double phase problems.

2. Mathematical background and hypotheses

Let (Ω, Σ) be a measurable space, X be a Polish space (that is, a complete, separable metrizable space), and $G : \Omega \rightarrow 2^X \setminus \{\emptyset\}$ be a multifunction. We say that the map G is “graph measurable”, if

$$\text{Gr } G := \{(z, x) \in \Omega \times X \mid x \in G(z)\} \in \Sigma \otimes B(X),$$

with $B(X)$ being the Borel σ -algebra of X . If μ is a complete and σ -finite measure on Ω , then the notion of graph measurability is equivalent to saying that for all $u \in X$, the map

$$z \mapsto d_X(u, G(z)) = \inf \{d_X(u, x) \mid x \in G(z)\}$$

is measurable, with d_X being a compatible metric on X . If μ is such a measure on Ω , X is a separable Banach space and $1 \leq r \leq \infty$, then

$$S_G^r := \{u \in L^r(\Omega, X) \mid u(z) \in G(z) \text{ for } \mu\text{-a.a. } z \in \Omega\}.$$

For a Banach space Y , we define

$$P_{fc}(Y) := \{C \subseteq Y \mid C \text{ is nonempty, closed and convex}\}.$$

Let Y be a reflexive Banach space such that Y^* is its topological dual, and denote by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ the duality brackets for the pair (Y^*, Y) . Let $A : Y \rightarrow 2^{Y^*}$ be a multivalued map.

Definition 2.1. We say that A is pseudomonotone if

- (a) for every $y \in Y$, $A(y) \in P_{fc}(Y)$ and A is bounded, that is, it maps bounded sets in Y to bounded ones in Y^* ;
- (b) for any sequence $\{(y_n, y_n^*)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \text{Gr } A$ such that

$$y_n \xrightarrow{w} y \text{ in } Y, y_n^* \xrightarrow{w} y^* \text{ in } Y^*, \text{ and } \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle y_n^*, y_n - y \rangle \leq 0,$$

we have $(y, y^*) \in \text{Gr } A$ and $\langle y_n^*, y_n \rangle \rightarrow \langle y^*, y \rangle$.

We say that $A : Y \rightarrow 2^{Y^*} \setminus \{\emptyset\}$ is “strongly coercive”, if

$$\frac{\inf \{\langle y^*, y \rangle \mid y^* \in A(y)\}}{\|y\|_Y} \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } \|y\|_Y \rightarrow \infty.$$

The importance of this class of maps, is based on the following theorem.

Theorem 2.2. A pseudomonotone and strongly coercive map is surjective.

For more on multifunctions and pseudomonotone maps, we refer to the books of Papageorgiou–Winkert [13] and Papageorgiou–Rădulescu–Repovš [14].

Our hypotheses on the multivalued perturbation are the following:

$H(F)$: $F : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow P_{fc}(\mathbb{R})$ is a multifunction such that

- (i) for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $(t, x) \mapsto F(t, x, y)$ is graph measurable;
- (ii) for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, $(x, y) \mapsto F(t, x, y)$ has a closed graph;
- (iii) there exists $\delta > 0$ such that

$$\inf \{h \in \mathbb{R} \mid h \in F(t, x, y)\} \geq 0$$

for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, all $0 \leq x \leq \delta$ all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$;

- (iv) there exist $\vartheta_0 > 0$, and $c^* > 0$, such that

$$c^* \vartheta_0^{-\eta} + h \leq 0$$

for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, and all $h \in F(z, \vartheta_0, 0)$;

(v) $|F(z, x, y)| = \sup\{|h| \mid h \in F(z, x, y)\} \leq \alpha(z) + c|y|^{\mu-1}$ for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, all $0 \leq x \leq \vartheta_0$, all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$ with $\alpha \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, $c > 0$, and $1 \leq \mu \leq p$.

Example 2.3. Consider the multifunction

$$F(z, x, y) = [f_-(z, x), f_+(z, x)] + \hat{c}|y|^{\mu-1},$$

with $\hat{c} > 0$ and measurable functions such that:

- for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, $f_-(z, \cdot)$ is lower semicontinuous;
- for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, $f_+(z, \cdot)$ is upper semicontinuous.

We assume that there exists $\delta > 0$ and $\vartheta_0 > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} f_-(z, x) &\geq 0 \quad \text{for a.a. } z \in \Omega, \text{ all } 0 \leq x \leq \delta, \\ f_+(z, \vartheta_0) &< 0 \quad \text{for a.a. } z \in \Omega. \end{aligned}$$

Then $F(z, x, y)$ satisfies hypotheses $H(F)$. We point out that if the reaction is $f(z, x) + \hat{c}|y|^{\mu-1}$, with $f(z, \cdot)$ having jump discontinuities, then at the discontinuity points we fill in the gaps by considering

$$f_-(z, x) = \liminf_{x' \rightarrow x} f(z, x'), \quad f_+(z, x) = \limsup_{x' \rightarrow x} f(z, x')$$

and the interval $[f_-(z, x), f_+(z, x)]$, which leads to multifunction as above.

Next, we will introduce the hypotheses on the map a in the differential operator. Let $\hat{\theta} \in C^1(0, \infty)$ with $\hat{\theta}(t) > 0$ for all $t > 0$. We assume that

$$0 < \hat{c} \leq \frac{\hat{\theta}'(t)t}{\hat{\theta}(t)} \leq c_0 \text{ and } c_1 t^{p-1} \leq \hat{\theta}(t) \leq c_2(t^{s-1} + t^{p-1})$$

for all $t > 0$, with $c_1, c_2 > 0$ and $1 < s < p$.

Then the hypotheses on the map a are the following:

$H(a)$: $a(y) = a_0(|y|)y$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, with $a_0(t) > 0$ for all $t > 0$ and

- (i) $a_0 \in C^1(0, \infty)$, $t \mapsto a_0(t)t$ is strictly increasing on $(0, \infty)$, $a_0(t)t \mapsto 0^+$ as $t \rightarrow 0^+$ and

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{a_0'(t)t}{a_0(t)} > -1;$$

- (ii) $|\nabla a(y)| \leq c_3 \frac{\hat{\theta}(|y|)}{|y|}$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \{0\}$, some $c_3 > 0$;

- (iii) $\langle \nabla a(y)\xi, \xi \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^N} \geq \frac{\hat{\theta}(|y|)}{|y|} |\xi|^2$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \{0\}$, all $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^N$.

These hypotheses lead to the following properties of the map a .

Lemma 2.4. *If hypotheses $H(a)$ hold, then*

- (a) $y \mapsto a(y)$ is continuous, strictly monotone (thus maximal monotone too);
- (b) $|a(y)| \leq c_4(|y|^{s-1} + |y|^{p-1})$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, some $c_4 > 0$;
- (c) $\langle a(y), y \rangle_{\mathbb{R}^N} \geq \frac{c_1}{p-1} |y|^p$ for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$.

We consider the Sobolev space $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, which by the Poincaré inequality can be equipped with the norm

$$\|u\| = \|Du\|_p \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

We also consider the map $V : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow W^{-1,p'}(\Omega) = W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)^*$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p'} = 1$ defined by

$$\langle V(u), h \rangle = \int_{\Omega} (a(Du), Dh)_{\mathbb{R}^N} dz \text{ for all } u, h \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

The map has the following properties (see Gasiński–Papageorgiou [15], Problem 2.192, p. 279).

Proposition 2.5. *If hypotheses $H(a)$ hold, then the map V is bounded, continuous, strictly monotone (hence maximal monotone too) and of type $(S)_+$, that is*

$$\text{“if } u_n \xrightarrow{w} u \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ and } \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle V(u_n), u_n - u \rangle \leq 0, \text{ then } u_n \rightarrow u \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)\text{”}.$$

From Papageorgiou–Rădulescu [2], we know that the following operators are covered by hypotheses $H(a)$:

- $\Delta_p u = \operatorname{div}(|Du|^{p-2} Du)$ with $1 < p < \infty$, (the p -Laplacian), then $a(y) = |y|^{p-2}y$.
- $\Delta_p u + \Delta_q u$ with $1 < q < p < \infty$ (the (p, q) -Laplacian), then $a(y) = |y|^{p-2}y + |y|^{q-2}y$.
- $\operatorname{div}(1 + |Du|^2)^{\frac{p-2}{2}} Du$ with $1 < p < \infty$ (the generalized p -mean curvature different operator), then $a(y) = (1 + |y|^2)^{\frac{p-2}{2}}y$.

3. A purely singular problem

In this section, we deal with the following auxiliary purely singular problem

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(Du(z)) = \lambda u(z)^{-\eta} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \end{cases} \tag{3.1}$$

with $\lambda > 0$ and $0 < \eta < 1$.

Let $C_0^1(\overline{\Omega}) := \{u \in C^1(\overline{\Omega}) \mid u|_{\partial\Omega} = 0\}$. This is an ordered Banach space with positive cone $C_+ := \{u \in C_0^1(\overline{\Omega}) \mid u(z) \geq 0 \text{ for all } z \in \overline{\Omega}\}$. This cone has a nonempty interior given by

$$\operatorname{int} C_+ := \left\{ u \in C_+ \mid u(z) > 0 \text{ for all } z \in \Omega \text{ and } \left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial n} \right|_{\partial\Omega} < 0 \right\}$$

with $\frac{\partial u}{\partial n} = (Du, n)_{\mathbb{R}^N}$ (the normal derivative of u), $n(\cdot)$ is the outward unit normal on $\partial\Omega$.

For problem (3.1), we have the following result which is of independent interest.

Proposition 3.1. *If hypotheses $H(a)$ hold and $\lambda > 0$, then problem (3.1) has a unique solution*

$$\bar{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int} C_+, \{\bar{u}_\lambda\}_{\lambda>0} \text{ is strictly increasing,}$$

(that is, if $0 < \lambda < \theta$, then $\bar{u}_\theta - \bar{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int} C_+$), and $\bar{u}_\lambda \rightarrow 0$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$.

Proof. The existence and uniqueness of the solution $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int} C_+$, follows from Proposition 11 of Papageorgiou–Rădulescu–Repovš [3]. Let $0 < \lambda < \theta$, we have

$$-\operatorname{div} a(D\bar{u}_\theta) \geq \lambda \bar{u}_\theta^{-\eta} \text{ in } \Omega. \tag{3.2}$$

We introduce the Carathéodory function $k_\lambda : \Omega \times (0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ defined by

$$k_\lambda(z, x) := \begin{cases} \lambda x^{-\eta} & \text{if } 0 < x < \bar{u}_\theta(z), \\ \lambda \bar{u}_\theta(z)^{-\eta} & \text{if } \bar{u}_\theta(z) \leq x. \end{cases} \tag{3.3}$$

Then, we consider the singular Dirichlet problem

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div} a(D(u(z))) = k_\lambda(z, u(z)) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \end{cases}$$

with $\lambda > 0$. As before, Proposition 11 of [3], implies that this problem has a unique solution $\tilde{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int} C_+$. We have

$$\langle V(\tilde{u}_\lambda), (\tilde{u}_\lambda - \bar{u}_\theta)^+ \rangle = \int_\Omega \lambda \bar{u}_\theta^{-\eta} (\tilde{u}_\lambda - \bar{u}_\theta)^+ dz \leq \langle V(\bar{u}_\theta), (\tilde{u}_\lambda - \bar{u}_\theta)^+ \rangle$$

(see (3.2) and (3.3)). So, from Proposition 2.5, we have that $\tilde{u}_\lambda \leq \bar{u}_\theta$. Then, $\tilde{u}_\lambda \in [0, \bar{u}_\theta] \cap \operatorname{int} C_+$ and so from (3.3), it follows that

$$\tilde{u}_\lambda = \bar{u}_\lambda$$

and thus the sequence $\{\bar{u}_\lambda\}_{\lambda>0}$ is nondecreasing. This implies

$$-\operatorname{div} a(D\bar{u}_\lambda) - \lambda \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} \leq (\theta - \lambda) \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} = -\operatorname{div} a(D\bar{u}_\theta) - \lambda \bar{u}_\theta^{-\eta} \text{ in } \Omega.$$

Then, Proposition 9 of Papageorgiou–Rădulescu–Repovš [3] implies that

$$\bar{u}_\theta - \bar{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int} C_+$$

and thus the sequence $\{\bar{u}_\lambda\}_{\lambda>0}$ is strictly increasing.

Let $\lambda \in (0, 1]$. We have

$$-\operatorname{div} a(D\bar{u}_\lambda) = \lambda \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} \text{ in } \Omega.$$

Acting on this equation with $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \operatorname{int} C_+$, we obtain

$$\frac{c_0}{p-1} \|D\bar{u}_\lambda\|_p^p \leq \lambda \int_\Omega \bar{u}_\lambda^{1-\eta} dz \leq \lambda c_4 \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|_p \leq \lambda c_5 \|\bar{u}_\lambda\|$$

for some $c_4, c_5 > 0$ (by Lemma 2.4, Hölder inequality and the continuity of the embedding $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^p(\Omega)$). So, we have

$$\|\bar{u}_\lambda\| \leq c_6$$

for some $c_6 > 0$ (since $1 < p$), thus

$$\bar{u}_\lambda \rightarrow 0 \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ as } \lambda \rightarrow 0^+.$$

From Lemma A1 of Giacomoni–Saoudi [16], we have

$$\|\bar{u}_\lambda\|_\infty \leq O(\|\bar{u}_\lambda\|) \text{ for all } 0 < \lambda \leq 1,$$

so

$$\bar{u}_\lambda \rightarrow 0 \text{ in } L^\infty(\Omega) \text{ as } \lambda \rightarrow 0^+.$$

Therefore, we conclude that

$$\bar{u}_\lambda \rightarrow 0 \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \text{ as } \lambda \rightarrow 0^+.$$

This completes the proof of this proposition. \square

4. Positive solutions

Using Proposition 3.1, we can find $\lambda^* \in (0, c^*]$ (see hypotheses $H(F)$ (iii) and (iv)) such that

$$0 \leq \bar{u}_\lambda(z) \leq \min\{\delta, \vartheta_0\} \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega, \text{ all } \lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]. \tag{4.1}$$

Let $N_F : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow 2^{L^{\mu'}(\Omega)}$ with $\frac{1}{\mu} + \frac{1}{\mu'} = 1$ be the multivalued Nemytskii map corresponding to the multifunction $F(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$, defined by

$$N_F(u) = S_{F(\cdot, u(\cdot), Du(\cdot))}^{\mu'} \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Proposition 4.1. *If hypotheses $H(F)$ hold, then for all $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ with $|u(z)| \leq \vartheta_0$ for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, we have*

$$N_F(u) \in P_{fc}(L^{\mu'}(\Omega)).$$

Proof. Using Proposition 2.8 of Ekeland–Temam [17, p. 316], we can find a sequence $\{v_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of piecewise affine functions such that

$$\begin{cases} |v_n(z)| \leq \vartheta_0 \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega, \text{ all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \\ \|Dv_n\|_p \rightarrow \|Du\|_p, \\ v_n \rightarrow u \text{ in } L^1(\Omega), \\ Dv_n \rightarrow Du \text{ in } L^1(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^N). \end{cases} \tag{4.2}$$

On account of hypothesis $H(F)$ (i) for all $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, we have that the map

$$z \mapsto F(z, v_n(z), y) \text{ is measurable.}$$

Since Dv_n is piecewise constant, it follows that

$$z \mapsto F(z, v_n(z), Dv_n(z)) \text{ is measurable for all } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Then by the Yankov-von Neumann–Aumann selection theorem (see Papageorgiou–Winkert [13], Theorem 2.7.75, p. 163), we can find $h_n : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a measurable function such that

$$h_n(z) \in F(z, v_n(z), Dv_n(z)) \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega,$$

so the sequence $\{h_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^{\mu'}(\Omega)$ is bounded (see hypotheses $H(F)$ (v) and (4.2)). We may assume that

$$h_n \xrightarrow{w} h \text{ in } L^{\mu'}(\Omega).$$

Using Theorem 8.38 of Hu–Papageorgiou [18, p. 486], we have

$$h(z) \in \overline{\text{conv}} \limsup F(z, v_n(z), Dv_n(z)) \subseteq F(z, u(z), Du(z)) \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega,$$

where we have used (4.2) and hypothesis $H(F)$ (ii). Clearly, $N_F(u)$ is closed and convex. Therefore, for all $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we have $N_F(u) \in P_{fc}(L^{\mu'}(\Omega))$. \square

From (4.1) and hypothesis $H(F)$ (iii), we see that

$$h(z) \geq 0$$

for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, all $h \in N_F(\bar{u}_\lambda)$ and all $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$. Therefore, we have

$$-\text{div } a(D\bar{u}_\lambda(z)) \leq \lambda \bar{u}_\lambda(z)^{-\eta} + h(z) \text{ in } \Omega \tag{4.3}$$

for all $h \in N_F(\bar{u}_\lambda)$ and $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$.

On the other hand, since $\lambda^* \leq c^*$, we obtain

$$\lambda \vartheta_0^{-\eta} + h(z) \leq c^* \vartheta_0^{-\eta} + h(z) \leq 0 \tag{4.4}$$

for a.a. $z \in \Omega$, all $h \in N_F(\bar{u}_\lambda)$. We introduce the truncation map $\hat{\tau} : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ defined by

$$\hat{\tau}(z) := \begin{cases} \bar{u}_\lambda(z) & \text{if } u(z) < \bar{u}_\lambda(z), \\ u(z) & \text{if } \bar{u}_\lambda(z) \leq u(z) \leq \vartheta_0 \text{ with } \lambda \in (0, \lambda^*], \\ \vartheta_0 & \text{if } \vartheta_0 < u(z). \end{cases} \tag{4.5}$$

Here, we recall that for $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$ and so $\bar{u}_\lambda \leq \vartheta_0$ for all $z \in \bar{\Omega}$. Now consider the map $\hat{\tau}_0 : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \times L^p(\Omega, \mathbb{R}^N)$ defined by

$$\hat{\tau}_0(u) := (\hat{\tau}(u), D\hat{\tau}(u)) \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Both maps $\hat{\tau}$ and $\hat{\tau}_0$ are continuous.

Now let $\hat{N} : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow P_{fc}(L^p(\Omega))$ be defined by

$$\hat{N}(u) := (N_F \circ \hat{\tau}_0)(u). \tag{4.6}$$

We know that the embedding $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^\mu(\Omega)$ is continuous and dense (by Sobolev embedding theorem). So, by Lemma 4.200 of Hu–Papageorgiou [18, p. 245], we have that the embedding $L^\mu(\Omega) = L^\mu(\Omega)^* \hookrightarrow W^{-1,p'}(\Omega) = W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)^*$ is continuous and dense. Therefore for any $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$, we can define the multivalued map $K_\lambda : W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \rightarrow P_{fc}(W^{-1,p'}(\Omega))$ by

$$K_\lambda(u) := V(u) - \lambda \hat{\tau}(u)^{-\eta} - \hat{N}(u) \text{ for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Proposition 4.2. *If hypotheses H(a) and H(F) hold and $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$, then K_λ is pseudomonotone.*

Proof. Let $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, $\{u_n^*\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq W^{-1,p'}(\Omega)$ be two sequences such that

$$\begin{cases} u_n^* \in K_\lambda(u_n) \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}, u_n \xrightarrow{w} u \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega), u_n^* \xrightarrow{w} u^* \text{ in } W^{-1,p'}(\Omega), \\ \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle u_n^*, u_n - u \rangle \leq 0. \end{cases}$$

From the definition of K_λ , we have

$$u_n^* = V(u_n) - \lambda \hat{\tau}(u_n)^{-\eta} - \hat{h}_n \text{ with } \hat{h}_n \in \hat{N}(u_n) \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{4.7}$$

Acting with $u_n - u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ on the above equation, we obtain

$$\langle u_n^*, u_n - u \rangle = \langle V(u_n), u_n - u \rangle - \int_\Omega [\lambda \hat{\tau}(u_n)^{-\eta} + \hat{h}_n] (u_n - u) dz \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{4.8}$$

Recall that $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int } C_+$ (see Proposition 3.1). Let

$$\hat{d}(z) = d(z, \partial\Omega) \text{ for all } z \in \bar{\Omega}.$$

Fixing $c_7 > 0$ such that

$$c_7 \hat{d} \leq \bar{u}_\lambda, \tag{4.9}$$

we have

$$\int_\Omega \left(\frac{|u_n - u|}{\bar{u}_\lambda^\eta} \right)^p dz = \int_\Omega \left(\bar{u}_\lambda^{1-\eta} \frac{|u_n - u|^p}{\bar{u}_\lambda} \right) dz \leq c_8 \int_\Omega \left(\frac{|u_n - u|}{\hat{d}_\lambda} \right)^p dz \leq c_9 \|D(u_n - u)\|_p^p$$

for some $c_8, c_9 > 0$ (recall that $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int } C_+$ and use (4.9)), where the last inequality is obtained by using Hardy’s inequality (see [3, p. 66]). So, we have that

$$\text{the sequence } \left\{ \frac{u_n - u}{\bar{u}_\lambda^\eta} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^p(\Omega) \text{ is bounded}$$

and thus

$$\text{the sequence } \left\{ \frac{u_n - u}{\bar{u}_\lambda^\eta} \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^1(\Omega) \text{ is uniformly integrable.}$$

From (4.7) and since $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^p(\Omega)$ compactly (by Sobolev embedding theorem), we see that at least for a subsequence the following holds

$$\frac{(u_n - u)(z)}{\bar{u}_\lambda(z)^\eta} \rightarrow 0 \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega.$$

Therefore, by Vitali’s convergence theorem, we have

$$\int_{\Omega} \bar{u}_{\lambda}^{-\eta} |u_n - u| dz \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Note that $\bar{u}_{\lambda} \leq \hat{\tau}(u_n)$ (see (4.5)). Hence $\hat{\tau}(u_n)^{-\eta} \leq \bar{u}_{\lambda}^{-\eta}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore, it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} \hat{\tau}(u_n)^{-\eta} |u_n - u| dz \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{4.10}$$

From (4.5) and hypothesis $H(F)(v)$, we see that

$$\{\hat{h}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^{\mu'}(\Omega) \subseteq L^{\beta'}(\Omega) \text{ is bounded,}$$

thus

$$\int_{\Omega} \hat{h}_n(u_n - u) dz \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{4.11}$$

We return to (4.8), pass to the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and use (4.7), (4.10) and (4.11). Based on Proposition 2.5, we obtain

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle V(u_n), u_n - u \rangle \leq 0,$$

so

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega). \tag{4.12}$$

For every $g \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we have

$$\langle u_n^*, g \rangle = \langle V(u_n), g \rangle - \int_{\Omega} [\lambda \hat{\tau}(u_n)^{-\eta} + \hat{h}_n] g dz \tag{4.13}$$

(see (4.7)). Note that

$$\langle u_n^*, g \rangle \rightarrow \langle u^*, g \rangle \text{ and } \langle V(u_n), g \rangle \rightarrow \langle V(u), g \rangle \tag{4.14}$$

(see (4.7) and (4.12)). From (4.5), for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\bar{u}_{\lambda} \leq \hat{\tau}(u_n) \leq \vartheta_0$$

so

$$\hat{\tau}(u_n)^{-\eta} \leq \bar{u}_{\lambda}^{-\eta} \leq c_{10} \hat{d}^{-\eta},$$

for some $c_{10} > 0$ (see (4.9)). So, as above using Hardy’s inequality and the Vitali convergence theorem, as well as the continuity of $\hat{\tau}$, we have

$$\int_{\Omega} \lambda \hat{\tau}(u_n)^{-\eta} g dz \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} \lambda \hat{\tau}(u)^{-\eta} g dz. \tag{4.15}$$

Note that $\hat{h}_n(z) \in F(z, \hat{\tau}(u_n)(z), D\hat{\tau}(u_n)(z))$ for a.a. $z \in \Omega$ and all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, so, we get

$$|\hat{h}_n(z)| \leq \alpha(z) + c |D\hat{\tau}(u_n)(z)|^{\mu-1} \tag{4.16}$$

for a.a. $z \in \Omega$ and all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. From (4.7), we see that

$$\{D\hat{\tau}(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^{\mu}(\Omega, \mathbb{N}) \text{ is bounded}$$

(recall $\mu < p$), so

$$\{\hat{h}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq L^{\mu'}(\Omega) \text{ is bounded}$$

(see (4.16)). Now, we may assume that

$$\hat{h}_n \xrightarrow{w} \hat{h} \text{ in } L^{\mu'}(\Omega). \tag{4.17}$$

So, as before, using Theorem 8.38, p. 486, of Hu–Papageorgiou [18], the continuity of $\hat{\tau}_0$ (see (4.12)) and hypothesis $H(F)(ii)$, we have

$$\hat{h}(z) \in F(z, \hat{\tau}(u)(z), D\hat{\tau}(u)(z)),$$

thus $\hat{h} \in \hat{N}(u)$.

Then, if in (4.13), we pass to the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and use (4.12), (4.14), (4.15) and (4.17), we obtain

$$\langle u^*, g \rangle = \langle V(u), g \rangle - \int_{\Omega} [\lambda \hat{\tau}(u)^{-\eta} + \hat{h}] g dz \text{ for all } g \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ and } \hat{h} \in \hat{N}(u).$$

It follows that $u^* \in K_{\lambda}(u)$. Moreover, from (4.7) and (4.12), we see that $\langle u_n^*, u_n \rangle \rightarrow \langle u^*, u \rangle$. Consequently, we conclude that K_{λ} is pseudomonotone. \square

Proposition 4.3. *If hypotheses $H(a)$, $H(F)$ hold and $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$, then K_λ is strongly coercive.*

Proof. Let $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and $u^* \in K_\lambda(u)$. Then,

$$u^* = V(u) - \lambda \hat{\tau}(u)^{-\eta} + \hat{h} \text{ with } \hat{h} \in \hat{N}(u).$$

Acting with $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u^*, u \rangle &= \langle V(u), u \rangle - \lambda \int_\Omega \hat{\lambda}(u)^{-\eta} u \, dz - \int_\Omega \hat{h} u \, dz \\ &\geq \frac{c_0}{p-1} \|Du\|_p^p - \lambda \int_\Omega \hat{\tau}(u)^{-\eta} u \, dz - \int_\Omega \hat{h} u \, dz \end{aligned} \tag{4.18}$$

(see Lemma 2.4). From the definition of $\hat{\tau}$ (see (4.5)), we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\lambda \int_\Omega \hat{\tau}(u)^{-\eta} u \, dz \\ &= \lambda \int_{\{u < \bar{u}_\lambda\}} \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} u \, dz + \lambda \int_{\{\bar{u}_\lambda \leq u \leq \vartheta_0\}} u^{1-\eta} \, dz + \lambda \int_{\{\vartheta_0 < u\}} \vartheta_0^{-\eta} u \, dz \\ &= \lambda \int_{\{u < \bar{u}_\lambda\}} \bar{u}_\lambda^{1-\eta} \frac{u}{\bar{u}_\lambda} \, dz + \lambda \int_{\{\bar{u}_\lambda \leq u \leq \vartheta_0\}} u^{1-\eta} \, dz + \lambda \vartheta_0^{-\eta} \int_{\{\vartheta_0 < u\}} u \, dz. \end{aligned} \tag{4.19}$$

From the proof of Proposition 4.2, since $\bar{u}_\lambda \in \text{int } C_+$, via Hardy's inequality, we infer that $\frac{u}{\bar{u}_\lambda} \in L^p(\Omega)$. Then from (4.19), we infer that

$$\lambda \int_\Omega \hat{\tau}(u)^{-\eta} u \, dz \leq \lambda c_{11} \|u\| \tag{4.20}$$

for some $c_{11} > 0$. Also, using hypothesis $H(F)(v)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_\Omega \hat{h} u \, dz \right| &\leq \int_\Omega \alpha(z) |u| \, dz + \int_\Omega c |D\hat{\tau}(u)|^{\mu-1} |h| \, dz \\ &\leq c_{12} (1 + \|u\|^\mu) \end{aligned} \tag{4.21}$$

for some $c_{12} > 0$. Returning to (4.18) and using (4.20), (4.21), we see that

$$\langle u^*, u \rangle \geq \frac{c_0}{p-1} \|u\|^p - c_{13} (1 + \|u\|^\mu)$$

for some $c_{13} > 0$. Therefore, it holds that K_λ is strongly coercive (recall that $\mu < p$). \square

Now, we can have the existence theorem for problem (1.1).

Theorem 4.4. *If hypotheses $H(a)$ and $H(F)$ hold, then for all $\lambda > 0$ small enough, problem (1.1) has a solution*

$$u_\lambda \in \text{int } C_+ \text{ and } u_\lambda(z) \leq \vartheta_0 \text{ for all } z \in \bar{\Omega}.$$

Proof. From Propositions 4.2 and 4.3, we know that for $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$ the map K_λ is pseudomonotone and strongly coercive. By Theorem 2.2, K_λ is surjective. So, we can find $\hat{u}_\lambda \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$0 \in K(\hat{u}_\lambda).$$

Therefore, we can find $\hat{h} \in \hat{N}(\hat{u}_\lambda)$ such that

$$V(\hat{u}_\lambda) = \lambda \hat{\tau}(\hat{u}_\lambda)^{-\eta} + \hat{h} \text{ in } W^{-1,p'}(\Omega) := W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)^*. \tag{4.22}$$

On (4.22) first, we act with $(\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Then, we have

$$\langle V(\hat{u}_\lambda), (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \rangle = \int_\Omega \lambda \hat{\tau}(\hat{u}_\lambda)^{-\eta} (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz + \int_\Omega \hat{h} (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz, \tag{4.23}$$

and

$$\int_\Omega \lambda \hat{\tau}(\hat{u}_\lambda)^{-\eta} (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz = \int_\Omega \lambda \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz \text{ (see (4.5)).}$$

Since $\lambda \in [0, \lambda^*]$, we have $\bar{u}_\lambda(z) \in [0, \delta]$ for all $z \in \bar{\Omega}$. Hence, $\hat{h}(z) \geq 0$ for a.a. $z \in \{\hat{u}_\lambda < \bar{u}_\lambda\}$ (see hypothesis $H(F)(iii)$), and

$$\int_\Omega \hat{h} (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz \geq 0.$$

Then from (4.23), we infer

$$\langle V(\hat{u}_\lambda), (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \rangle \geq \int_\Omega \lambda \bar{u}_\lambda^{-\eta} (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \, dz = \langle V(\bar{u}_\lambda), (\bar{u}_\lambda - \hat{u}_\lambda)^+ \rangle,$$

where we have used Proposition 3.1. Hence, from Proposition 2.5, we have $\bar{u}_\lambda \leq \hat{u}_\lambda$.

Next in (4.22), we act with $(\hat{u}_\lambda - \vartheta_0) \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ to find

$$\langle V(\hat{u}_\lambda), (\hat{u}_\lambda - \vartheta_0)^+ \rangle = \int_{\Omega} [\lambda \vartheta_0^{-\eta} + \hat{h}(z)] (\hat{u}_\lambda - \vartheta_0)^+ dz$$

(see (4.5)). Note that $D\hat{\tau}(\bar{u}_\lambda)(z) = 0$ for a.a. $z \in \{\vartheta_0 < \hat{u}_\lambda\}$. Hence,

$$\hat{h}(z) \in F(z, \vartheta_0, 0) \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega.$$

Since $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$ and $\lambda^* \leq c^*$, from hypothesis $H(F)(iv)$, we have

$$\lambda \vartheta_0^{-\eta} + \hat{h}(z) \leq 0 \text{ for a.a. } z \in \Omega.$$

So, finally, we obtain

$$\langle V(\hat{u}_\lambda), (\hat{u}_\lambda - \vartheta_0)^+ \rangle \leq 0 = \langle V(\vartheta_0), (\hat{u}_\lambda - \vartheta_0)^+ \rangle,$$

so $\hat{u}_\lambda \leq \vartheta_0$.

We have proved that

$$\hat{u}_\lambda \in [\bar{u}_\lambda, \vartheta_0],$$

so \hat{u}_λ is a positive solution of (1.1) for $\lambda \in (0, \lambda^*]$ (due to (4.5)).

Whereas, the nonlinear regularity theory of Lieberman [1] implies that $\hat{u}_\lambda \in \text{int } C_+$. \square

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yunru Bai: Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Leszek Gasiński:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration. **Nikolaos S. Papageorgiou:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank the two knowledgeable referee for their helpful remarks.

Funding

This project has received funding from the Natural Science Foundation of Guangxi Grant Nos. 2021GXNSFFA196004 and GKAD21220144, NNSF of China Grant Nos. 12001478, 12101143 and 12371312, and the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 823731 CONMECH.

References

- [1] Lieberman GM. The natural generalization of the natural conditions of Ladyzhenskaya and uraltseva for elliptic equations. *Comm Partial Differential Equations* 1991;16:311–61.
- [2] Papageorgiou NS, Rădulescu VD. Coercive and noncoercive nonlinear Neumann problems with indefinite potential. *Forum Math* 2016;28:545–71.
- [3] Papageorgiou NS, Rădulescu VD, Repovš DD. Nonlinear nonhomogeneous singular problems. *Calc Var Partial Differential Equations* 2020;59:31.
- [4] Bai Y, Gasiński L, Papageorgiou NS. Nonlinear nonhomogeneous Robin problems with dependence on the gradient. *Bound Value Probl* 2018;2018:24.
- [5] Papageorgiou NS, Rădulescu VD, Repovš DD. Positive solutions for nonlinear Neumann problems with singular terms and convection. *J Math Pures Appl* 2020;136:1–21.
- [6] Papageorgiou NS, Scapellato A. Nonlinear singular problems with convection. *J Differential Equations* 2021;296:493–511.
- [7] Papageorgiou NS, Zhang Y. Nonlinear nonhomogeneous Dirichlet problems with singular and convection terms. *Bound Value Probl* 2020;2020:21.
- [8] Zeng S, Liu Z, Migórski S. Positive solutions to nonlinear nonhomogeneous inclusion problems with dependence on the gradient. *J Math Anal Appl* 2018;403:432–48.
- [9] El Manouni S, Marino G, Winkert P. Existence results for double phase problems depending on Robin and Steklov eigenvalues for the p-Laplacian. *Adv Nonlinear Anal* 2022;11(1):304–20.
- [10] Zeng S, Papageorgiou NS. Positive solutions for (p, q) -equations with convection and a sign-changing reaction. *Adv Nonlinear Anal* 2022;11(1):40–57.
- [11] Zhang J, Niu R, Han X. Positive solutions for a nonhomogeneous Schrödinger-Poisson system. *Adv Nonlinear Anal* 2022;11(1):1201–22.

- [12] Papageorgiou NS. Double phase problems: a survey of some recent results. *Opuscula Math* 2022;42(2):257–78.
- [13] Papageorgiou NS, Winkert P. *Applied nonlinear functional analysis*. Berlin: De Gruyter; 2018.
- [14] Papageorgiou NS, Rădulescu VD, Repovš DD. *Nonlinear analysis theory and methods*. Switzerland: Springer; 2019.
- [15] Gasiński L, Papageorgiou NS. *Existence in analysis. Part 2: Nonlinear analysis*. Cham: Springer; 2016.
- [16] Giacomoni J, Saoudi K. $W_0^{1,p}$ Versus C^1 local minimizers for a singular and critical function. *J Math Anal Appl* 2010;363:697–710.
- [17] Ekeland I, Temam R. *Convex analysis and variational problems*. Oxford-New York: North Holland-American Elsevier; 1976.
- [18] Hu S, Papageorgiou NS. *Research topics in analysis. Volume I: Grounding theory*. Cham: Birkhäuser; 2022.